

TESTING OF Z-PINNED LAMINATES WITH MULTIPLE DELAMINATIONS

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Keywords: Through thickness reinforcement, multiple delaminations, Z-pinning, Mode II testing

ABSTRACT

Application of Z-pinning is a subject of great interest in the field of through-thickness reinforcement (TTR) of composite laminates. This method provides the reinforcements necessary to resist the growth of delamination in laminated composites. To date, the majority of Z-pin characterisation work has been conducted on fracture coupons containing a single embedded delamination. In contrast, when thick composite components are subjected to impact loading, multiple delaminations are generated. An End Loaded Split (ELS) test method was selected to generate controlled, mode II, multiple delaminations to interact with the pinned region. The ELS specimen was modified with two embedded delaminations of different lengths, placed at specific depths through the thickness. A longer crack was placed near the top surface and a shorter crack near the bottom. Numerical models were used to optimise the geometry of the specimen to ensure that each delamination propagated independently.

In the unpinned control samples, the longer upper crack initiated first followed by unstable growth to the clamped end. Further loading triggered unstable growth of the lower crack. With the addition of Z-pins, it was shown that the delaminations were arrested; the upper delamination initially, followed by the lower delamination. Once both delaminations had reached the Z-pinned region, they propagated simultaneously in a stable manner. These results highlight the ability of the Z-pins to arrest mode II delaminations at multiple levels through the thickness. Additionally they provide a much needed data set for validation and verification of Z-pin numerical modelling tools.

1 INTRODUCTION

Laminated fibre reinforced (FRP) composites possess poor interlaminar properties and are thus susceptible to delamination from impact, monotonic and cycling loading during service. Delamination damage causes significant reduction in the stiffness of the composite structure, which may lead to premature catastrophic failure. The test case of a single delamination is well understood and thus reliable prediction as well as prevention can be implemented, however in practice composite structures seldom fail through single delaminations. Often multiple simultaneous delaminations may be formed, typically during dynamic loading.

Multiple delaminations have been subject of extensive studies over the years specifically within areas of in-plane compression and buckling of composite laminates with post impact damage, with the majority of focus being on development of simplified modelling tools to understand the interaction of such delaminations with one another [1–3].

Multiple inter-layer cracks have significant influence on the response of a system to external loading, thus modelling such systems can be quite complex. To design an experimental test configuration for analysing interaction of multiple delaminations finite element (FE) analyses have been adopted, with each individual delamination explicitly modelled using the Abaqus/Explicit

implementation of cohesive contact.

Through thickness reinforcement (TTR) technologies for composite materials have been shown to improve the resistance of the structure to delaminations. One of these techniques, known as Z-pinning, involves insertion of small diameter fibrous or metallic pins, through the thickness of a laminated composite material. This reinforcement process is performed prior to final cure and results in a composite structure with a significantly increased delamination resistance capability.

To date the majority of Z-pin characterisation work has been conducted on simple fracture tests such as Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) or End Notched Flexure (ENF) specimens containing a single embedded delamination [4-5]. In contrast, when thick composites are subjected to impact loading, multiple delaminations are generated which is the result of complex damage formation and interactions between matrix cracks, fibre failures and delaminations [6-8]. The effectiveness of TTR pins to resist the propagation of multiple delamination is yet to be tested and analysed under controlled conditions.

It has been shown that embedded pins interact with the composite material on a structural level [9-10], in that the embedded length of the pins relative to the crack plane has a direct influence on its suppression of delamination propagation. For this reason the reinforcement capability of a pin, may be affected when more than one delamination is resisted. This investigation aims to understand whether the pins are capable of resisting multiple simultaneous delaminations to the same level as a single delamination configuration. However in order to fully characterise this behaviour a test has to be created whereby controlled multiple delamination propagations are generated.

In this investigation a test configuration was designed such that the interaction of multiple delaminations with a region of TTR pins can be reliably analysed. In this way a set of experimental results has been generated to reliably validate TTR modelling tools in development.

2 MATERIALS, MANUFACTURING AND METHODS

Multiple delaminations are typically observed when a composite structure undergoes out of plane loading. Delaminations formed in this manner can be regarded as predominantly Mode II dominated. For this reason it was decided to modify a well-established mode II fracture toughness test method in the End Loaded Split (ELS) test. This procedure involves the deflection of a pre-cracked cantilever beam. However, for the purpose of this investigation multiple cracks distributed through the thickness were embedded in the test specimen. To develop controlled multiple mode II delaminations to interact with the pinned region, this multiple ELS (MELS) specimen was embedded with two different delamination lengths placed at specific depths through the thickness, similar to those studied analytically by Andrews *et al.* [11].

Four requirements needed to be satisfied when designing the MELS specimen configuration:

1. Resistance of pinned laminates to delamination has been shown to be different for a unidirectional (UD) relative to a non-UD stacking sequence [9]. Therefore the stacking sequence of the specimens for this investigation has to be non-UD.
2. The stacking sequence of the entire beam including the delaminated sections must be symmetric i.e. no extensional coupling must be present when subjected to bending
3. Delamination must propagate only between two 0° plies
4. The two delaminations must propagate independently i.e. each delamination initiation has to correspond to a distinguishable applied load.

In order to satisfy the first three requirements, the following quasi-isotropic (QI) stacking sequence was adopted: $(0,-45,90,45)_s // [(0,-45,90,45)_s]_2 // (0,-45,90,45)_s$

For an individual ply thickness of 0.125mm, this results in a beam with a nominal thickness, h of 8mm with the through thickness position of the upper, a_U and lower, a_L delaminations at $0.25h$ from

top and bottom surfaces respectively.

To satisfy the fourth requirement, a detailed FE analysis was carried out to examine the MELS configuration behaviour to varying the lengths a_U and a_L . An FE model of the MELS setup was created using the explicit formulation of the ABAQUS FE package. A 1mm wide strip section of the specimen was meshed with 8-noded linear brick elements (C3D8) 1mm in size. Bilinear cohesive contact was enabled at the delamination surfaces with non-cohesive contact properties in the normal direction defined as “hard” i.e. no interpenetration allowed with a transverse direction friction coefficient of 0.3 applied.

From the length variation analysis, the desired delamination growth behaviour that satisfied the fourth requirement gave a configuration with a_U and a_L lengths of 56 mm and 32 mm respectively. This was chosen for the experimental testing (Fig. 1).

Specimens were manufactured using IM7/8552 prepreg (Hexcel, UK) to achieve a nominal thickness of 8mm with a 13 μ m PTFE film placed at the desired locations. Having the starter crack between two 0° plies prevents any out of plane crack migration.

Figure 1: ELS Specimen configuration highlighting the through thickness position of the upper (a_U) and lower (a_L) delaminations (dimensions in mm)

The TTR specimens were pinned with T300 carbon/BMI pins arranged in a grid with a spacing of 1.75mm generating a nominal 2% areal density. An example of the regularity and the success rate of the pin insertion is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Representative ELS sample with pinned TTR highlighting the high level of regularity with more than 95% full penetration success rate (a) Top and bottom view of the sample (b) Polished cross section

Cross section microscopy presented in Fig. 3, indicates little disturbance of the laminate region surrounding the pins, with little evidence of ply crimping. All the pins in the specimens for this

investigation were found to be misaligned by an approximate 8° from the nominal vertical axis, which is an artefact of the insertion method used. This results in a loading mode mixity, ϕ of 99%, as determined by Yasaei *et. al.* [9]. Six replicates of both the unpinned and pinned configurations were cut from the same panel, with a width of 20mm.

The specimens were fixed into an ELS test fixture with a nominal 5N/m torque applied on the four retaining screws of the clamp. Using a calibrated Instron test machine with a 10kN load cell, the load was applied to the specimen at a displacement rate of 2mm/min. The resulting values of Load, P , and displacement, δ , were recorded until full propagation of each crack to the clamped end.

Figure 3: Cross section view of an inserted pin, showing no noticeable ply crimping

3 RESULTS

A representative load plot of a control unpinned sample is presented in Fig. 4 alongside the results predicted from the FE analysis, showing good agreement for prediction of both load drops. The delamination sequence for the control sample is shown in Fig. 5. Both delaminations propagated independently in an unstable manner to the clamped end of the specimen.

Figure 4: Representative load vs. displacement plot of the unpinned ELS sample alongside those predicted numerically using FE

Figure 5: Delamination propagation sequence for control samples (Delaminations highlighted for clarity)

A representative load vs. displacement plot of a pinned sample is shown in Fig. 6 alongside the results of an unpinned sample. The initiation of the upper delamination occurred at approximately the same load as the control samples, however the unstable propagation was immediately arrested by the z-pins. With further loading the upper delamination propagated to a length of ~72mm (Fig. 7), until the strain energy release rate (SERR) of the lower delamination reached a critical value, initiating an unstable propagation to the same length as the upper delamination, ~72mm. With further loading, both delaminations grew simultaneously in a stable manner until reaching the clamped end.

Figure 6: Representative load vs. displacement plot of the unpinned alongside pinned ELS sample

Figure 7: Delamination propagation sequence for pinned samples (Delaminations highlighted for clarity)

4 IN-SITU PIN DEFORMATION

To observe the pin deformation during delamination propagation in detail, one pinned sample was polished until a single column of pins was visible on the side cross-section. This surface was then treated with a thin layer of transparent epoxy. This specimen was then loaded using the same procedure as previously described. A snapshot of the loaded specimen at the point where both upper and lower delaminations have propagated towards the clamp is shown in Fig. 8. The individual deformation of each row of pins is clearly visible. It is interesting to see that the pins have not fractured but exhibit small amounts of pull-out whilst being deformed in bending. The pins are not being loaded in pure mode II due to the small opening observed (Fig. 9).

Figure 8: In-situ observation of TTR pins undergoing deformation during delamination growth

Figure 9: Schematic of the pin deformation behaviour when subjected to unconstrained mode II loading

An SEM micrograph of a pinned ELS specimen tested in mode II is shown in Fig. 10. Pin rupture has resulted in a vacated channel on one fracture surface whilst on the opposite surface the split and fractured pin protruding from its channel is evident.

Figure 10: SEM micrographs of carbon composite pin failing in a mode II ELS test

9 CONCLUSIONS

An experimental procedure has been presented where controlled, multiple mode II delaminations are produced to assess the susceptibility of TTR pins to two independently propagating cracks. The test configuration was finalised following a comprehensive numerical analysis using FE models. In this process a system of cracks was identified to produce the desired delamination propagation behaviour where two delaminations propagated independently from one another. This independence is ideal in that the initiation and propagation can be identified clearly.

Following the identification of the desired test configuration, experimental tests were carried out to verify the predicted models and to observe the interaction of two independent cracks with TTR pins. Samples with TTR pins were shown to arrest the two independent delaminations, however subsequent stable propagation of the delaminations occurred simultaneously.

A closer look at the nature of deformation of pins as delamination propagates through the samples allowed confirmation of the pin pull-out and bending failures observed in previous experimental tests. Although the testing procedure was in theory pure mode II, the failure process of the pins generates some out of plane opening and results in a rupture of the pins which is akin to a high mode mixity loading regime.

These tests provide vital data for validation of modelling tools being developed. These tools have been created based on assumptions of single crack growth through a pinned region.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge Rolls-Royce plc for their support of this research through the Composites University Technology Centre (UTC) at the University of Bristol, UK.

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